

Solvent Extraction Separation of Titanium from Aqueous Oxalate Solution with Tri-n-octylamine

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The use of tri-n-octylamine (TOA) as liquid anion-exchanger in the quantitative and selective extraction of titanium(IV) from aqueous oxalate medium is reported. The effects of different parameters on the extraction behaviour have been studied. The method has been used in the estimation of titanium in some river clay samples.

THE extraction behaviour of various metal ions with different high molecular weight amines dissolved in suitable inert diluents have been reviewed by several authors¹⁻³. Among the most widely used materials of this class, tri-n-octyl amine deserves special mention. The extraction of several cations using TOA have been reported in literature². However only a little attention was paid to the extraction behaviour of titanium with TOA³, in which the metal ion was extracted from aqueous perchlorate medium.

In the present paper, we report a systematic study on the extraction of titanium(IV) from aqueous oxalate solution with TOA dissolved in benzene. The effects of pH, diluents and other parameters have been studied. The method has been applied for the estimation of titanium in several clay samples collected from the Ib river, Orissa, India.

Experimental

Tri-n-octyl amine (E. Merck) used as such was converted into sulphate form by the usual method⁴. All other reagents used were of A.R. grade.

A stock solution of titanium was prepared by dissolving recrystallised and air-dried $K_2TiO \cdot (C_2O_4)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (3.68 g) in concentrated H_2SO_4 (100 ml) containing $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ (8 g) and it was diluted to 1 lit and standardised by cupferron method⁵.

Procedure: An aqueous phase (2 ml) containing 25 μg Ti^{IV} complexed with oxalic acid and adjusted to required pH by the addition of acid or alkali, was equilibrated with TOA-sulphate in benzene (10 ml; 0.1 M TOA + 1 M H_2SO_4) for 5 min. The organic layer was separated and metal ion was stripped back with saturated sodium oxalate solution. The stripped solution was then estimated for Ti by spectrophotometric method using chromotropic acid⁶. All the extractions were carried out at 27°.

Results and Discussion

The optimum pH range for maximum extraction was found to be 4.5–5.5. Solution of 0.1 M TOA

in different diluents were investigated. The phase volume ratio was 1 : 1 as otherwise emulsion was formed. With respect to the percentage extraction in different diluent, the order is benzene > toluene > xylene > nitrobenzene > chlorobenzene > chloroform > carbon tetrachloride > diethyl ether > cyclohexane > butan-1-ol > isoamyl alcohol. The extraction and stripping were complete in 5 min. For maximum extraction of Ti the concentrations of both oxalic acid and amine were 0.1 M.

The Ti^{IV} extract was stripped with 10 ml of various concentrations of NaOH, NH_3 , HCl, HNO_3 , H_2SO_4 , H_3PO_4 and Na-oxalate. Sodium oxalate was found to be the most suitable stripping agent. The alkalis were unsuitable as they accelerated hydrolysis of titanium as well as promoted emulsion formation. Optimum concentration of titanium for almost quantitative extraction was in the range 10^{-4} – 10^{-1} M in a single extraction with 0.1 M TOA in benzene. The log-log plot of the concentration of metal ion in organic phase against concentration of metal ion in aqueous phase yield a straight line showing that the distribution of metal ion is practically independent on its concentration and no polymeric species are formed in organic layer.

Effect of diverse ions: Titanium (25 ppm) was extracted from the binary mixtures of various ions within $\pm 2\%$ error (the ion concentration is indicated in the parenthesis): Na, K, Mn^{II} , Be^{II} (2000 ppm each); Mg^{II} , Pb^{II} , Gd^{III} , Dy^{III} , Nd^{III} , Pr^{III} (1000 ppm each); Se^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} , Al^{III} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , La^{III} , Mo^{VI} , UO_2^{II} , sulphate, phosphate, silicate (750 ppm each); VO^{II} , Nb^V , Ta^V , Th^{IV} , Zr^{IV} , Hf^{IV} fluoride (350 ppm each).

The separation of Ti (25 ppm) was possible in presence of more than one foreign ion in the following mixtures within $\pm 2\%$ error: (a) Ti^{IV} (25 ppm) + Zr^{IV} (100 ppm) + Hf^{IV} (50 ppm) + Zn^{II} (25 ppm); (b) Ti^{IV} (25 ppm) + Fe^{III} (50 ppm) + Al^{III} (50 ppm) + Na^+ (100 ppm); (c) Ti^{IV} (25 ppm) + fluoride (100 ppm) + sulphate (100 ppm) + Na^+ (100 ppm); (d) Ti^{IV} (25 ppm) + fluoride (100 ppm) + phosphate (100 ppm) + Al^{III} (50 ppm).

Nature of extracted species: The log-log plots of the variation of distribution coefficient (K_D) of Ti^{IV} with oxalate ion concentration at a fixed amine concentration and variation of K_D with amine concentration at fixed oxalate concentration yield straight lines with slope 1.8 and 2.1 respectively. This indicated the involvement of the following extraction equilibria,

where, R = n-octyl group.

Application: The clay samples (~0.5 g) collected from the Ib river (Orissa) was fused with anhydrous sodium carbonate in Pt-crucible, the fused mass was leached with hot water and filtered. The precipitate was dissolved in 1 : 20 sulphuric acid and collected in a volumetric flask. The solution was analysed for Ti^{IV} content after triplicated extraction with TOA in benzene by the proposed method and the results were checked by the recovery of known quantity metal ion added (Tables 1 and 2).

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF TITANIUM(IV) IN CLAY SAMPLES

Sample no.*	Amount of Ti in stock solution ppm	Amount of Ti after separation* ppm
1	800	796.9
2	810	814.5
3	825	826.6
4	840	837.8
5	850	856.2
6	1000	996.0
7	1200	1202.5
8	1400	1438.2
9	1500	1464.0
10	1600	1608.0

*Average of 3 determinations.

TABLE 2—RECOVERY OF TITANIUM IN CLAY SAMPLES

Sample no.*	Amount added ppm	Amount found ppm	Recovery %
1	0	796.9	
	10	812.2	100.6
	20	831.5	101.7
	30	834.3	100.8
10	0	1608.0	
	10	1612.3	99.64
	20	1625.7	99.85
	30	1631.5	99.60

*As Table No. 1.

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